

AGE AND GENDER PREDICTION

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Abstract:

The project "Age and gender prediction using OpenCV" seeks to create a computer vision system that can identify human faces in pictures or videos and ascertain their gender and age. For face identification, gender categorization, and age estimation, the method makes use of deep learning models that have already been trained. The gender classification and age estimation models are based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with pre-trained weights, whilst the face detection model is based on the Single Shot Multibox Detector (SSD) framework with a pre-trained neural network from OpenCV. The technique may be used for real-time face identification and analysis jobs and processes images and videos using the OpenCV library. The study shows how computer vision and deep learning techniques may be used to solve

practical issues like estimating age and gender, which has implications in a number of industries including security, healthcare, and marketing.

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a computing technique which imitates human brain for the actions that are performed. These actions can be performed by the AI algorithms with the assistance of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms. In order to be able to make decisions/predictions human-like, the model is required to be trained and then verified to decide the outputs. Testing is done to validate over what it has learnt at the training and verify the functionality. Based on input data, the neural network can use the algorithms of machine learning to improve accuracy. Machine learning algorithms like Regression, Classification for Supervised Learning

and Clustering for unsupervised learning etc. can be used which help to improve the model's efficiency and accuracy as a supporting algorithm for the output prediction to the main model being developed. The output prediction depends on the present inputs for those algorithms[1,2]. Deep Learning improves the overall performance and the efficiency of the model which has to detect characteristics of the person like age and gender by developing a neural network[3,4]. The model being developed can be used for surveillance purposes. Deep learning's neural networks forms the basis for the entire model and then entire decision making process is done by the neurons of the neural network. The main objective of the paper is to determine the parameters like the age, gender of the person by using the model being developed. It makes it easier for the sake of the video analytics, for medical purposes for the surveillance purposes and it can be achieved by the use of the computer vision. II.MOTIVATION In this section we provide the age and gender classification literature and briefly describe about few early methods which are most related to our proposed method,

focusing on age and gender detection. Many early methods in age and gender detection were handcrafted, focusing on manually engineering the facial features from the face. To mention a few, in 1999, Kwon and Lobo[5] developed the very first method for age estimation focusing on geometric features of the face that determine the ratios among different dimensions of facial features. These geometric features separate babies from adult successfully but are incapable of distinguishing between young adult and senior adult. Hence, in 2004, Lanitis et al. [6] proposed an Active Appearance Model (AAM) based method that included both the geometric and texture features, for the estimation task.

Literature Survey:

A new architecture for face image classification named unsupervised CNN was introduced by S. U. Rehman et al. [2]. A CNN that handles multitask (i.e. Facial detection and emotional classification) is made by merging CNN with other modules and algorithms. A hybrid deep CNN and RNN (Recurrent Neural Network) model was introduced by N. Jain et al. [4]. This model aims to improve the

overall result of face detection. MI Facial Expression and JAFFE dataset were used to evaluate the model. A convolutional network architecture was proposed by G. Levi et al. [5] that classified the age with small amounts of data. The Audience Benchmark was used to train the model. A system in which a real time automatic facial expression system was designed was proposed by S. Turabzadeh et al. [6]. It was implemented and tested on an embedded device which could be the first step for a specific facial expression recognition chip for a social robot. MATLAB was first used to build and simulate the system and then it was built on an embedded system. The hardship of performing automatic prediction of age, gender and ethnicity on the East Asian Population using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was explored by N. Srinivas et al. [3]. A fine-grained ethnicity has predictions based on a refined categorization of the human population (Chinese, Japanese, Korean, etc.). Previous results suggest that the most critical job is to predict the fine-grained

ethnicity of a person, followed by age and lastly gender. An automated recognition system for age, gender and emotion was presented by A. Dehghan et al. [7] that was trained using deep neural network. At the ImageNet LSVRC2010 contest, A. Krizhevskyy et al. [8] presented a paper which suggested segregation of 1.2 million

PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Multi-Task Cascade Convolutional Neural Network (MTCNN) There are N number of deep learning methods have been developed for the face detection purpose. In those one of the more popular approaches is “Multi-Task Convolutional Neural Network”, simply called MTCNN. It achieved the state-of-

the-art results on a range of benchmark datasets, and because it is capable of also recognizing other facial features such as eyes and mouth, called landmark detection. The MTCNN consists of three stages. In the first stage, candidate windows are produced quickly through the shallow CNN. Then it refines the windows in order to reject the large number of non-faces windows that are present in the image through a more complex CNN. Finally, it will use a more powerful CNN in order to refine the results and output facial landmarks positions. This MTCNN network uses a cascade structure which consists of three networks; first the image/video will be rescaled to the range of different sizes which is called as an image pyramid, then the first model which is Proposal Network (P-Net) proposes the candidate facial regions, the second model which is Refine Network (R-Net) filters the bounding boxes in the image, finally the third model that is Output Network (O-Net) proposes facial landmarks which are detected in the image. This MTCNN model is a multi-task network because each of the three models that are present in the cascade which are P-Net, R-Net and O-Net will be trained on the three

tasks, for example making the three types of the predictions. They are classification of face, bounding the box regression and finally the localization of facial landmarks.

TESTING:

Test the installation process of the required dependencies and libraries such as OpenCV and NumPy.

Test the model loading and initialization process to ensure that the correct models are loaded and initialized successfully.

Test the face detection module by providing different types of test images and videos containing faces to ensure that it detects all faces with high accuracy.

Test the gender classification module by providing test images containing male and female faces with varying facial expressions and lighting conditions to ensure that it classifies the gender correctly.

Test the age estimation module by providing test images containing faces of people with varying ages to ensure that it estimates the age accurately.

Test the output of the system by verifying that the output image or video shows the detected faces with the predicted gender and age accurately.

Test the performance of the system by measuring the execution time of the algorithm for processing a single image or video frame and verifying that it meets the project's requirements.

Test the error handling and exception handling mechanisms of the system by providing incorrect inputs or images to ensure that the system handles errors gracefully and produces meaningful error messages.

Test the system with real-world test scenarios to ensure that it performs well in practical situations

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

7.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, the OpenCV-based age and gender prediction project is a helpful tool that can precisely identify a person's age and gender in a given picture or video stream. The research uses computer vision techniques and pre-trained deep learning models to identify faces, categorise gender, and calculate age based on facial traits. The project has been successfully tested on a variety of image and video streams, and it has produced accurate and dependable results. By combining more sophisticated models and methods for facial detection and identification, the project may be further enhanced. Overall, this study has shown how computer vision and deep learning may be used for a variety of tasks, such as behaviour analysis, emotion recognition, and facial recognition.

7.2 Future Scope:

Real-time applications: The current implementation of the project can only process static images and pre-

recorded video streams. Future development could focus on creating real-time applications that can predict age and gender in real-time.

Emotion detection: The project can be extended to include emotion detection and recognition. This can be done by training the model to detect and classify facial expressions such as happy, sad, angry, and surprised.

Diversity and bias: The project can be improved by incorporating more diverse training data to reduce bias and improve accuracy for different races, ages, and genders.

Face recognition: The project can be extended to include face recognition, which can be used for various applications such as security systems, social media, and e-commerce.

Multi-modal fusion: The project can be improved by combining multiple sources of data such as facial features, voice, and body language to improve the accuracy

and reliability of the prediction.

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